

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE EXPOSITION OF NORTH AMERICA OF THE TASHKENT BOTANICAL GARDEN (UZBEKISTAN)

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Abstract

The article provides brief information about the North American exposition of the Tashkent Botanical Garden of Uzbekistan. The species of plants growing today in this exposition are given.

Keywords: Botanical garden, Uzbekistan, exposition, North America, dendroflora, introduction, perspective, decorative, tree, shrub.

It is known that Botanical Gardens are scientific organizations that protect nature with rare plants, and are also engaged in the introduction and research of plants. The main objectives of the Botanical Gardens are the protection of biodiversity, the creation of a collection of flora in order to enrich the local flora, as well as scientific and educational work. The introduced plants in the Botanical Garden are arranged by geographical origin. Plants from regions with similar climates are grown outdoors, and introduced species from tropical and subtropical regions are grown in greenhouses and greenhouses, where similar microclimatic conditions are created for them, similar in their homeland.

Tashkent Botanical Garden named after Academician F.N. Rusanov at the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan was organized in 1944. To date, more than 6 thousand woody-shrubby and herbaceous plant species have been introduced to the Tashkent Botanical Garden. In the Tashkent Botanical Garden, introduced plants belonging to various floras are located in the expositions of North America, Europe-Crimea-Caucasus, Far East, Central and East Asia. Visitors to the garden can get acquainted with new introductions, representatives of foreign flora and get the necessary information about them. The North American exposition of the Tashkent Botanical Garden was first created in 1950-1951 in the northeastern part of the garden. Its area is 9 hectares. Trees and shrubs belonging to 38 families, 62 genera and 183 species grow in the exposition.

The woody and shrubby plants in the expositions of the Botanical Garden are grown mainly from seeds obtained from other gardens by seed exchange, or from vegetative organs brought directly from the USA by the founder of the garden, academician F.N. Rusanov, such as: almond willow (*Salix amygdaloides* Anders.), California hazel (Hazelnut) – *Corylus cornuta* subsp. *californica* (A.DC.) A.E. Murray, blue elderberry (*Sambucus caerulea* var. *caerulea*), feather-shaped mahonia (*Mahonia pinnata* (Lam.) Fedde), etc. These plants were brought from the eastern United States. Flora

from the western United States are represented in a limited number of exhibits.

At the beginning of the route, Virginia juniper (*Juniperus virginiana* L.) grows from coniferous trees, as well as western Thuja (*Thuja occidentalis* L.). Marsh cypress (*Taxodium distichum* (L.) Rich.) is planted along the shores of the reservoir. This species is a coniferous species. In natural conditions, this species grows in swamps and along riverbanks in the eastern United States. The species has a powerful and widely developed root system and has a solid wood that does not rot in water. In local conditions, it grows well in the presence of irrigation and along the shores of water sources, it is also frost-resistant (up to -30 °C). Surrounded by stately marsh cypresses, an aquatic lotus (*Nymphaea odorata* f. *rosea*) grows in an artificial pond. Frost-resistant and drought-resistant shrub Amorpha (*Amorpha fruticosa* L.) grow on the opposite shore of the reservoir. The fragrant smell of beautiful flowers of this species attracts bees. Also here you can find long-leaved willow (*Salix longifolia* Muhlenb.) and almond-shaped willow (*Salix amygdaloides* Anders.), belonging to American willow species. They have bright green leaves, which are highly decorative.

Among American poplars, there are: tall poplar (*Populus candicans* Ait.) and deltoid poplar (*Populus deltoides* W. Bartram ex Marshall), common in the northern states of the USA and Canada. Along the route, 5 species of nuts grow on the left side of the path. Among them, a very interesting species is the steppe rocky walnut (*Juglans rupestris* Engelm.). The leaves are narrow-leaved, the nuts are small, with a diameter of 1-2 cm. In its natural range, it forms self-seeding plants that are resistant to summer drought and abnormal winter frosts. Along the route on the right there are 5 species of Carya nut – *Carya laciniosa* (Michx. Loud.), bitter nuts – Heart-shaped Carya (*Carya cordiformis* (Wangh.) K. Koch), ovoid Carya (*Carya ovata* Mill. K. Koch), White Carya (*Carya alba* Koch Nut) and Carya pecan (*Carya pecan* (Marsh.) Engl.). *Carya pecan* has a durable wood, the nut kernel contains up to 65% oil. Next, there is the Virginia Spearhead (*Ostrya virginiana*) and the American Hornbeam (*Carpinus*

americana Michx.). After them, let's pay attention to the paper birch (*Betula papyrifera* Marsh.). This species is the most decorative species in the USA.

About 50 species of oak (*Quercus*) are common in the flora of the USA. 5 species have been introduced to the Botanical Garden. White oak (*Quercus alba* L.) and large-fruited oak (*Quercus macrocarpa* Michx.) grow here. There is a whole oak grove in the garden. In the garden there are species that, in addition to seed reproduction, are also propagated by root offspring, these are bicolor oak (*Quercus bicolor* Willd.) and Gambel oak (*Quercus gambelii* Nutt.). *Asimina triloba* (L.) Dun.) is the northernmost representative of the subtropical and tropical genus *Asimina* Adans. In the USA, the range of this species reaches the latitude of New York. The species in the Botanical Garden grows well, in early autumn the leaves turn yellow and fall off, is frost-resistant, tolerates frosts up to -27°C without damage. Because of the red flowers, this species turns into an ornamental tree during flowering. In September, fruits ripen that taste like ripe bananas. The conditions of the garden allow the successful growth of this fruit crop. The tulip tree (*Liriodendron tulipifera*) was introduced to Uzbekistan at the end of the XIX century. It blooms

luxuriantly, has good seed productivity, but the seeds have low germination. The tree has spherical bluish-green leaves and large flowers of dark yellow and orange-pink color, resembling tulips. The Botanical Garden has propagated and transferred about 10 thousand seedlings of this species for landscaping the city of Tashkent.

An evergreen shrub grows near the tulip tree – holly-leaved magonia (*Magonia aquifolium* Pursh), is one of the few species in the garden, characterized by high frost resistance. On the right side, *Mahonia pinnata* (Lag.) Fedde. grows under the Frame trees. On the left side of the mashrut grow species with peculiar ruddy flowers and fragrant calicanthus wood – *Calycanthus floridus* L., *C. fertilis* Walt, and *C. occidentalis* Hook. Moving along the route, we meet with a hybrid sycamore – maple-leaved sycamore (*Platanus acerifolia* (Ait.) Wild.) and Western sycamore (*P. occidentalis* L.). On both sides of the road there are species belonging to the genus Hawthorn (*Crataegus* L.). The collection of this genus in the garden is considered the richest. There are over 20 species of the *Crataegus* genus here alone.

a

b

c

d

Species of the North American exposition in the Tashkent Botanical Garden:
Cercis canadensis L. (a); *Calycanthus floridus* L. (b);
Mahonia aquifolium (Pursh) Nutt. (c); *Magnolia soulangeana* Soul. -Bod. (d)

In the garden, representatives of the Leguminosae family grow: *Gleditsia vulgaris* or tricolored (*Gleditsia triacanthos* L.), as well as a species with a small number of grains in short beans – hybrid (*G. texana* Bagd.).

The most beautiful, new tree for Uzbekistan is the yellow Kladrastis (*Cladrastis kentukea* (Dum. Cours.) Rudd). Smooth, dark gray trunks, shiny foliage and white flowers in hanging inflorescences turned it into a

highly decorative woody species. The trees in the garden bear fruit and give a few plants from self-seeding. The bunduk or Kentucky coffee tree (*Gymnocladus dioica* (L.) K. Koch.) was introduced to Uzbekistan at the beginning of the last century. In the garden it is represented by a whole grove, and they grow well. This arboreal species is dioecious. Species of sumac (*Rhus*) of North American origin in the garden formed a beautiful landscape. Along with completely harmless species and even edible ones – acetic sumac (*Rhus typhina* L.), three-lobed sumac (*R. trilobata* Nutt.) is also found at the same time. Sumac species are very decorative, especially in autumn wilting colors. Species of maple (*Acer*) in autumn with their red-yellow leaves are highly decorative and certainly catches the eye. These include the sugar maple (*A. saccharum* Marsh.), first introduced to Uzbekistan.

The genus Linden (*Tilia*) in the flora of America is represented by two species, these species are *Tilia americana* and *T. neglecta*. On the right along the route, there are species of horse chestnut: pavia chestnut (*Aesculus pavia* L.), octagonal chestnut (*A. octandra* Marsh.), naked chestnut (*A. glabra* Willd.) and inconspicuous chestnut (*A. neglecta* Lindl.). They bloom beautifully in spring and bear fruit abundantly, and at the end of summer they lose their foliage early and, unlike other species, enter the winter dormancy early. The garden has an almost exhaustive rich collection of species of wild American, *Vitis* L. grapes. All of them are characterized by great winter hardiness, heat and dry resistance, bloom abundantly and bear fruit. They have intensive growth, rise to the tops of trees and spread over the surface of the soil. In nature, wild grape species reproduce by seeds and produce abundant self-seeding. Of the rare species, the round-leaved grape (*Vitis rotundifolia* (Lam.) DeFlers), introduced by the garden, draws attention. The most beautiful in foliage is the blue-leaved grape (*Vitis cinerea* Engel M.). Species of the genus *Parthenocissus* Planch. are also represented here.

The Virginian persimmon (*Diospyros virginiana* L.) is particularly distinguished by its high yield. Its fruits are edible and fragrant. Among the ash trees there

are blue ash (*Fraxinus quadrangulata* Michx.), Tumei ash (*F. toumey* Britt.), Biltmore ash (*F. biltmoreana* Beadle), *F. tomentosa* Michx., *F. velutina* Torr. and *Fraxinus nigra* Marsh., *F. oregona* Nutt., *F. velutina* Torr. and its form is f. *glabra*. Yucca species are concentrated on the circular area. Among them are arboreal – high yucca (*Yucca elata* Engelm.), glorious yucca (*Y. gloriosa* L.); narrow-leaved – medium yucca (*Y. intermedia* Me Kelvey), yucca.glaucous (*Y. glauca* Nutt.); more broad-leaved-filamentous yucca (*Y. filamentosa* L.) and hard yucca (*Y. rigida* Tre1.). For the first time introduced into the Botanical Garden, agave-leaved yucca (*Y. pallida* Ms. Kelvey) is a promising species for landscaping. To the north of the site there are catalpa groves consisting of *Catalpa bignonioides* Walt. and catalpa beautiful (*C. speciosa* Warder). Some of the trees are wrapped in a liana tube flower (*Campsis radicans* (L.) Seem.) with large dark red tubular flowers. In their undergrowth grow species of snowberry (*Symphoricarpos* DuRoi.), species of the genera elderberry (*Sambucus* L.) and *Viburnum* L. In early April, when other parts of the arboretum are in greenery and even partially in bloom, the American site is striking with its lagging spring vegetation. The dendroflora of this part is adapted to the sharply continental climate of the USA and Canada. This, in particular, explains the fact that Uzbekistan, with its sharply continental climate, has a predominance of North American breeds in urban plantations and forest plantations.

References

1. Vafin R.V., Putenikhin V.P. Hawthorns: introduction and biological features // Monograph. – M.: Nauka, 2003. – 224 p. (in Russian).
2. Zalesov S.V., Platonov E.P. and others. Studying the prospects of tree introductions // Methodological guidelines for the course “Increasing forest productivity” for masters in the fields of “Forestry”, “Landscape gardening and landscape construction”. – Yekaterinburg, 2014. (in Russian).
3. Dedenko T.P., Khazova E.P. Introduction of decorative tree and shrub species. – Voronezh, 2015. – 95 p. (in Russian).